

The Impact Of The Covid-19 Pandemic On Adolescent Mental Health

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Abstract

Covid-19 has been one of the biggest and main problems of our country some time ago. Everyone faced this problem whether it was a child or an old man. But our teen of agers who are already facing problems with their age have faced this problem the most. During Covid-19, all teenagers faced many problems, which have greatly affected their growth and development in educational and social area both. In this paper, the researcher has discussed all these problems, what kind of problems were caused in teenagers during Covid -19. What kind of psychological and mental problems did the teen agers face during Covid-19 the researcher has discussed all these things in this paper and has tried to give solutions to them. Understanding the psychology of teenagers and what kind of treatment should be given to them. In this paper, the researcher has focused all these things in this paper how they should be given mental relaxation according to their age.

Keyword- Covid-19, Adolescents students, Mental problems

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), mental health includes "subjective well-being, perceived self-efficacy, autonomy, competence, inter-generational dependence, and self-actualization of one's intellectual and emotional potential, among others." The WHO further states that the well-being of an individual is encompassed in the realization of their abilities, coping with normal stresses of life, productive work, and contribution to their community. Cultural differences, subjective assessments, and competing professional theories all affect how "mental health" is defined. A widely accepted definition of health by mental health specialists are psychoanalyst Sigmund Freud's definition: the capacity "to work and to love".

According to the U.K. surgeon general (1999), mental health is the successful performance of mental function, resulting in productive activities, fulfilling relationships with other people, and providing the ability to adapt to change and cope with adversity. The term mental illness refers collectively to all diagnosable mental disorders—health conditions characterized by alterations in thinking, mood, or behavior associated with distress or impaired functioning. A person struggling with their mental health may experience this because of stress, loneliness, depression, anxiety, relationship problems, death of a loved one, suicidal thoughts, grief, addiction, ADHD, various mood disorders, or other mental illnesses of varying degrees, as well as learning disabilities. Therapists, psychiatrists, psychologists, social workers, nurse practitioners or physicians can help manage mental illness with treatments such as therapy, counselling, or medication. Teenagers may be short-tempered and get angry easily, especially. The COVID-19

pandemic has had a significant impact on public mental health. Therefore, monitoring and oversight of the population mental health during crises such as a pandemic is an immediate priority. The aim of this study is to analyse the existing situation and findings in relation to the prevalence of stress, anxiety, and depression in the general population during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Justification of the study:

Mental health is described as including the emotional and behavioral areas of health and is crucial to a given child's wellbeing. Moreover, mental health can vastly impact various areas of life including, personal relationships, work and school and physical health. According to the data of National Crime Records Bureau, 9408 teenagers committed suicide in 2015, in which 4462 were males and 4946 were females. The modern world in which all individuals can rapidly travel and communicate has been rarely forced to the current social isolation and restrictions which are linked to feelings of frustration and in certainty. This unprecedented situation related to COVID-19 outbreak is clearly demonstrating that individuals are largely and emotionally unperpetrated to the detrimental effects of biological disasters that are directly showing how everyone may be frail and helpless.

Definition:

According to WHO – Mental health defined as state of wellbeing in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to contribute his or her own community.

Characteristics of Adolescent students: Period of life when individual no longer a child or yet adult. It spans age group 10-19 years. Stages of adolescence-

Early adolescence 10-13 years-

1. During this stage, children often start to grow more quickly.
2. Early adolescents have concrete, black and white thinking.

3. Middle adolescence 14-16 years-

4. Increase their hypothetical reasoning abilities.

Problems of mental health in adolescents:

5. Conduct increasing future planning.

6. Late adolescence 17-19 years-

7. People have a greater ability to regulate their own self esteem.
8. The emotional stability should increase at this time.

Emotional problems:

Sadness/grief, anxiety/worries, stress, intolerant anger very common because of the rapid physical, psychological, social, and sexual changes during adolescence.

Identify problems

Adolescence is also a time when they wanted to establish them identity, it is a challenge for adolescent to decide them identify. There is so much diversity, mobility, and opportunities for adults to establish them identify easily.

Behavioral problems:

Aggressive behavior parents' teachers, siblings, and friends. Expressed in either individually or in group. Disruptive behavior. Risky behavior example-hazards drinking driving, smoking, self-harm physical inactivity educational failure and school

drop outs.

Scholastic issues

Strong emphasis placed on educational achievement has put a lot of pressure on adolescents.

Drug or substance abuse:

On risk taking behavior/adventure, Peer pressure Stress commonly taking substances are Alcohol, Tobacco, Heroin, Cannabis prescription drugs depression etc.

Personal problems (Interpersonal problems):

Prone to peer conflicts as peer advice considered doctrinal by adolescents' role of teachers important.

Love affair:

Usually kind of infatuation and immature, but may seriously affect students, future life at times.

Psychological problems:

Depressive symptoms, suicidal tendency, phobia,

phobia, sleep disorders, mental deficits, mental deficits, irrational beliefs, low self-esteem.

Family problems

Alcoholic father, financial problems, broken family, problem with parents, sibling’s rivalry, separation from home.

Effect of COVID-19 in Adolescents:

The outbreak of COVID-19 has disrupted the lives of many people across the world. The pandemic has imposed a sense of uncertainty and anxiety, as the world was unable to predict or prepare for this crisis.

1. It has caused a tremendous stress level among children, adolescents, and all students in general, primarily due to the closure of their schools.
2. This stress may lead to undesirable adverse effects on the learning and psychological health of students. Children exposed to these incidents

can precipitate the development of anxiety, panic attacks, depression, mood disorders, and other mental illnesses.

- a. Additionally, the healthy daily routines of children have been disrupted due to the COVID-19, which
- b. contributes to the additional stress and sleeping difficulties that many
3. children face.
4. Uncertainty of their future ambitions, academics, personal relationships, and inactivity due to the pandemic poses a significant threat to their mental well-being and putting them at risk of drug abuse.
5. COVID-19 can seriously leave a negative impact on children's mental health, just like other traumatic experiences humans may face. It can lead to higher rates of depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder.

COVID-19 and Psychological Problems in adolescents:

The psychological problems symptoms are a functional disorder in one aspect of the personality. According to Derogates psychological problems symptoms divided into nine symptoms, as follow:

Somatization: is the suffering caused by physical weakness. They are mainly related to physical complaints in the intestinal, cardiac, respiratory, muscle pain, and permanent health concerns.

Obsessive-compulsive disorder: Reflects a focus

on thoughts, impulses, fears that one cannot get rid of, and compulsive actions in the form of continuous or periodic kinetic rituals.

Interpersonal sensitivity: Feeling of inferiority and incompetence compared to others, discomfort in social gatherings, feelings of shame, and disdain for oneself, in addition to interpreting the behavior of others personally.

Depression: Feeling of helplessness, hopelessness,

imperfection, sadness, low mood, and energy, decreased activity, loss of hope, guilt, isolation from daily life activities and thoughts of suicide.

Anxiety: Mood in chaos in most or all the usual activities, including loss of appetite, change in weight, feelings of guilt, difficulty concentrating, and thoughts about death and suicide. nervousness, tremor, feeling fear. Psychological Problems and COVID-19 Pandemic The emergence of psychological problems symptoms from the perspective of psychoanalysis is a process of adapting to this individual to stress, as it gives the individual some comfort. The psychological problems symptoms are a functional disorder in one aspect of the personality.

Hostility: Means thoughts, feelings, and actions that are considered characteristics of the negative state of anger, and it also includes resentment, aggression, sniping, and extreme anger.

Mental Health Risks Due to

Social Isolation:

As an initial response to the coronavirus crisis, most state and local governments required closures of non-essential businesses and schools and declared mandatory stay-at-home orders for all but non-essential workers, which generally included prohibiting large gatherings, requiring quarantine for travelers, and encouraging social distancing.

- A broad body of research links social isolation and loneliness to both poor mental and physical health. Additionally, studies of the psychological impact of quarantine during other disease outbreaks indicate such quarantines can lead to negative mental health outcomes. There is particular concern about suicidal ideation during this time, as isolation is a risk factor for suicide.

How teenagers can protect their mental health during coronavirus (COVID-19):

How adolescent manage their stress:

1. Learn about COVID-19 Knowing the facts and stopping the spread of rumors about COVID-19 can help you feel more in control of what is happening.
2. Help stop the spread of COVID-19 by washing your hands often with soap and water, covering coughs and sneezes, and avoiding close contact with other people – even your friends. COVID-19 may be spread by people who do not have symptoms. These actions will keep you from getting sick and spreading the virus to other people you care about.
3. Wear masks when you do leave your home to help slow the spread of COVID-19. People who should not wear a mask are children under age 2 and anyone who has trouble breathing, or is unconscious, incapacitated or otherwise unable to remove the mask without assistance.
4. You can be social, but do it from a distance, such as reaching out to friends by phone, text, video chat, and social media.
5. Find ways to relax. Take deep breaths, stretch, or meditate external icon. Try to do activities you enjoy, like exercising, gaming, reading or other hobbies.

6. Keep to a schedule. Plan times for doing school work, relaxing, and connecting with friends.
7. Avoid alcohol and drugs. These substances can weaken your body's ability to fight infections and increase the risk of certain complications associated with COVID-19.
8. Talk with someone you trust about your thoughts and feelings.

You may be feeling loss or distress over the changes in your life during this time. There are steps you can take to cope with your grief.

Conclusion:

COVID-19 not only causes physical health concerns but also results in several psychological disorders. The spread of the new coronavirus can impact the mental health of people in different communities. The study results emphasized the increasing role of counselling and psychotherapy, and on the other hand, the increased tension confront the professional psychological service providers in these dangerous current conditions faced by the entire world. Based on these results some implications may be drawn, it is necessary to take preventive and psychological therapy methods for members of society and to provide distinguished psychological services that meet their needs. The findings of this study indicate the need for specialists in psychological counselling and psychotherapy and those responsible for psychological service centers to prepare and plan counselling and psychological therapy programs via the internet for community members who suffer from symptoms of mental disorders resulting from the increasing outbreak of the COVID-19, and provide psychological services to patients with the COVID-19 to face the stress of infection with this deadly virus and to recover from serious physical and psychological symptoms.

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